

A Study on a Fractional Algebraic Problem

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Abstract: In this paper, we study a fractional algebraic problem based on a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions. We can solve this fractional algebraic problem by using some techniques. In fact, the solutions are generalizations of the solutions of ordinary algebraic problem.

Keywords: Fractional algebraic problem, New multiplication, Fractional analytic functions.

I. INTRODUCTION

Fractional calculus is a branch of mathematical analysis which deals with the research and applications of integrals and derivatives of arbitrary order. In recent decades, the applications of fractional calculus in various fields of science is growing rapidly, such as applied mathematics, physics, bioengineering, mechanics, control theory, electrical engineering, modelling, financial economics, etc [1-12].

In this paper, based on a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions, a fractional algebraic problem is studied. Using some methods, the solutions of this fractional algebraic problem can be obtained. On the other hand, our results are generalizations of the results of classical algebraic problem.

II. PRELIMINARIES

Definition 2.1 ([13]): Assume that x and a_k are real numbers for all k , and $0 < \alpha \leq 1$. If the function $f_\alpha: [a, b] \rightarrow R$ can be expressed as an α -fractional power series, that is, $f_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_k}{\Gamma(k\alpha+1)} x^{k\alpha}$, then we say that $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ is α -fractional analytic function.

In the following, we introduce a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions.

Definition 2.2 ([14]): If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$. Suppose that $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ and $g_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ are two α -fractional analytic functions,

$$f_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_k}{\Gamma(k\alpha+1)} x^{k\alpha} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_k}{k!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes k}, \tag{1}$$

$$g_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_k}{\Gamma(k\alpha+1)} x^{k\alpha} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_k}{k!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes k}. \tag{2}$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} & f_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes g_\alpha(x^\alpha) \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_k}{\Gamma(k\alpha+1)} x^{k\alpha} \otimes \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_m}{\Gamma(m\alpha+1)} x^{m\alpha} \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\Gamma(k\alpha+1)} \left(\sum_{m=0}^k \binom{k}{m} a_{k-m} b_m \right) x^{k\alpha}. \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

Equivalently,

$$\begin{aligned}
 & f_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes g_\alpha(x^\alpha) \\
 &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_k}{k!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha\right)^{\otimes k} \otimes \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_k}{k!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha\right)^{\otimes k} \\
 &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k!} \left(\sum_{m=0}^k \binom{k}{m} a_{k-m} b_m\right) \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha\right)^{\otimes k}. \tag{4}
 \end{aligned}$$

Definition 2.3 ([15]): If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$, $g_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ are two α -fractional analytic functions. Then $(f_\alpha(x^\alpha))^{\otimes n} = f_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes \dots \otimes f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ is called the n th power of $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$. On the other hand, if $f_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes g_\alpha(x^\alpha) = 1$, then $g_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ is called the \otimes reciprocal of $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$, and is denoted by $(f_\alpha(x^\alpha))^{\otimes -1}$.

III. MAIN RESULTS

In this section, we solve a fractional algebraic problem. At first, we need a lemma.

Lemma 3.1: Suppose that $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, p, t are real numbers, and n is a positive integer. If $\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} t^\alpha = p$, then

$$\left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} t^\alpha\right]^{\otimes n} = \frac{n! \cdot [\Gamma(\alpha+1)]^n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} \cdot p^n \tag{5}$$

Proof Since $t^\alpha = \Gamma(\alpha + 1) \cdot p$, it follows that

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} t^\alpha\right]^{\otimes n} \\
 &= \frac{n!}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} t^{n\alpha} \\
 &= \frac{n!}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} (t^\alpha)^n \\
 &= \frac{n!}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} [\Gamma(\alpha + 1) \cdot p]^n \\
 &= \frac{n! \cdot [\Gamma(\alpha+1)]^n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} \cdot p^n.
 \end{aligned}$$

Q.e.d.

Problem 3.2: Assume that $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and λ is a real number, $\lambda \neq 0$. If

$$\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \otimes \left[\left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha\right]^{\otimes 2} - \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + 1 \right]^{\otimes -1} = \lambda. \tag{6}$$

Find

$$\left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha\right]^{\otimes 2} \otimes \left[\left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha\right]^{\otimes 4} - \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha\right]^{\otimes 2} + 1 \right]^{\otimes -1}, \tag{7}$$

and

$$\left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha\right]^{\otimes 3} \otimes \left[\left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha\right]^{\otimes 6} - \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha\right]^{\otimes 3} + 1 \right]^{\otimes -1}. \tag{8}$$

Solution Since

$$\left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha\right]^{\otimes -1} \otimes \left[\left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha\right]^{\otimes 2} - \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + 1 \right] = \frac{1}{\lambda}. \tag{9}$$

It follows that

$$\left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha\right] + \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha\right]^{\otimes -1} = \frac{1}{\lambda} + 1. \tag{10}$$

Let

$$\left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} r^\alpha \right]^{\otimes -1} = \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 2} \otimes \left[\left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 4} - \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 2} + 1 \right]^{\otimes -1}. \tag{11}$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} r^\alpha \\ &= \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right]^{\otimes -2} \otimes \left[\left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 4} - \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 2} + 1 \right] \\ &= \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 2} + \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right]^{\otimes -2} - 1 \\ &= \left[\left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right] + \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right]^{\otimes -1} \right]^{\otimes 2} - 3 \\ &= \frac{2 \cdot [\Gamma(\alpha+1)]^2}{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\lambda} + 1 \right)^2 - 3. \quad (\text{by Lemma 3.1}) \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 2} \otimes \left[\left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 4} - \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 2} + 1 \right]^{\otimes -1} \\ &= \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} t^\alpha \right]^{\otimes -1} \\ &= \frac{1}{\frac{2 \cdot [\Gamma(\alpha+1)]^2}{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)} \left(\frac{1}{\lambda} + 1 \right)^2 - 3}. \end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

On the other hand, let

$$\left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} s^\alpha \right]^{\otimes -1} = \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 3} \otimes \left[\left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 6} - \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 3} + 1 \right]^{\otimes -1}. \tag{14}$$

Then by Lemma 3.1,

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} s^\alpha \\ &= \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right]^{\otimes -3} \otimes \left[\left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 6} - \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 3} + 1 \right] \\ &= \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 3} + \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right]^{\otimes -3} - 1 \\ &= \left[\left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right] + \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right]^{\otimes -1} \right]^{\otimes 3} - 3 \left[\left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right] + \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right]^{\otimes -1} \right] - 1 \\ &= \frac{6 \cdot [\Gamma(\alpha+1)]^3}{\Gamma(3\alpha+1)} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\lambda} + 1 \right)^3 - 3 \left(\frac{1}{\lambda} + 1 \right) - 1. \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 3} \otimes \left[\left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 6} - \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right]^{\otimes 3} + 1 \right]^{\otimes -1} \\ &= \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} s^\alpha \right]^{\otimes -1} \\ &= \frac{1}{\frac{6 \cdot [\Gamma(\alpha+1)]^3}{\Gamma(3\alpha+1)} \left(\frac{1}{\lambda} + 1 \right)^3 - 3 \left(\frac{1}{\lambda} + 1 \right) - 1}. \end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, based on a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions, we study a fractional algebraic problem. In fact, the fractional algebraic problem is a generalization of traditional algebraic problem. By some methods, we can find the solutions of this fractional algebraic problem. In the future, we will continue to use the new multiplication of fractional analytic functions to solve the problems in applied mathematics and fractional differential equations.

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